

Role of Substrate Symmetry in Gas-Solid Reactions. Part II: Structural Interpretation of the Reactions of Gaseous Oxide

M. D. Karkhanavala

The importance of symmetry in determining the course of chemical reactions involving a solid and gaseous UO_2 is pointed out and the possible advantage of this type of reaction in the synthesis of chemical compounds discussed.

The role of substrate symmetry in epitaxy is well known. However, the role of symmetry in chemical reactions involving solids is not generally appreciated. Yet in reactions between solids the symmetry of the reactants plays an important part leading to widespread solid solution and compound formation between apparently chemically dissimilar substances but containing ions of nearly the same sizes, and charges which could be balanced to give overall electrical neutrality. As a result of this, one often finds in naturally occurring minerals unusual combinations of chemical elements.¹ This knowledge has recently been exploited in the synthesis of unusual commercially important compounds in the spinel, perovskite and garnet groups²—compounds which do not exist in nature and which have been "tailor-made" to meet specific requirements.

In this report the importance of symmetry in determining the course of 'chemical' reactions involving a solid and a gas (gaseous UO_2) is pointed out and the possible advantage of this type of reaction in the synthesis of chemical compounds is discussed.

SYMMETRY CONSIDERATIONS

The results of the reactivity of the gaseous uranium oxide with other oxides reported in part I are interesting, in that though most of the oxides chosen belonged to the same group (IV) in the periodic table and hence should have exhibited similar chemical behaviour, actually they behaved quite differently. This difference cannot be accounted for solely on the basis of the normal gradation of properties as one goes down the particular group.

The fact that the real deciding factor in determining the reactivity is the symmetry and not the apparent chemical composition or even the ionic radius, is brought out by the behaviour of ZrO_2 above and below its phase transformation temperature range (1100-1200°).

- (a) Bragg, "Atomic Structure of Minerals" Cornell Univ. Press, 1938.
- (b) Ramberg, "Origin of Metamorphic and Metasomatic Rocks", Chicago Univ. Press, 1958.
- (c) Van Arkel, "Molecules and Crystals in Inorganic Chemistry", Butterworth, London, 1949.
- (d) Dunlap, "Introduction to Semiconductors". Wiley, 1960.
- (e) Jona and Shirane, "Ferroelectric Crystals", Pergamon Press, 1962.

The non-reactivity with ZrO_2 below or just above the transformation temperature cannot be attributed to the relatively lower concentration of gaseous UO_2 at those temperatures, for there is obviously sufficient UO_2 present to react strongly with ThO_2 or even with stabilized ZrO_2 at the same and even lower temperatures (1100°- to 1250°). Reaction with ThO_2 has been observed³ even at 1000°. It has therefore to be concluded that this non-reactivity with ZrO_2 below about 1300° is only due to the nonsuitable structure and symmetry of the substrate.

Ackermann *et al*⁴ have shown that the gaseous uranium oxide formed at high temperatures by the reaction of U_2O_5 and oxygen is monomeric UO_2 . The symmetry of gaseous monomeric UO_2 molecule is not known but it can be reasonably assumed to be of the pyramidal AX_2 type, with the C_{2v} point group symmetry. The planar AX_2 type with the D_{2h} point group symmetry is unlikely on the basis of ionic radii of uranium U^{6+} (0.8 Å) and oxygen O^{2-} (1.40 Å).

Chapman⁵ has very recently suggested that the gaseous uranium oxide formed may be UO_4 though this is assumed to be present close to the UO_2 composition only. While this has not been corroborated, the point group symmetry of the monomeric UO_4 molecule, if it exists, would in all probability be T_d .

UO_2 , ThO_2 and their solid solution have the fluorite structure [space group: $Fm\bar{3}m$] which has a three fold axis of symmetry along the $\{111\}$ axis. Also in this space group the forms in the order of decreasing importance are $[111]$, $[100]$, $[110]$, $[311]$, and $[331]$. In case of UO_2 single crystals the crystals habit was found⁶ to differ slightly with the method of preparation but in all cases the most pronounced crystal habit was $[111]$. In case of naturally occurring ThO_2 also⁷, $[111]$ is the pronounced habit and twinning is known to take place along the $[111]$.

In the $[111]$ plane, the distribution of the anions with respect to a cation is along the corners of two equilateral triangles one above and one below the cation and with apexes in opposite directions (Fig. 1). In UO_2 and ThO_2 the two triangles would be separated by 1.59 and 1.62 Å. Further the point group symmetry of such surface cation with respect to the oxygens in the plane below it would be C_{2v} .

Hence when the gaseous monomeric UO_2 comes into contact with a solid substance like ThO_2 , with a predominant $[111]$ habit in which the surface cations would have a matching C_{2v} symmetry, almost every collision of the gaseous molecule with the solid surface would be a 'sticking' collision and the molecule would not bounce back. Thus 'chemical' reaction would take place leading to an oxygen-excess non-stoichiometric solid solution. It must be pointed out that since in UO_2 or ThO_2 , the anions form a continuous network with the triangles sharing sides, the gaseous UO_2 molecules would initially in all probability occupy isolated sites and only when the concentration increases would

3. Karkhanavala, Momin, George, Singh, Damani and Amirthalingam, Paper No. 749, 3rd Int. Conf. on Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy, Geneva, 1964.
4. Ackermann, Thorn, Alexander, Zetenbaum, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 350.
5. Chapman, and Meadows, ORNL 3313; 4th Conf. on Reactor Materials Chemistry, October 1963, Gatlinburg, Tenn., USA.
6. Robins, Wilks, Bradbury; AERE/M933. Atomic Energy Research Establishment, Harwell.
7. Palache, Berman, and Frondel (Editors): "Dana's System of Mineralogy", Vol. I., p. 620; John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, 1944)

these begin to share the corner oxygens. This could lead simultaneously to the expulsion of an oxygen ion as an oxygen atom, releasing two electrons and the conversion of U^{6+} ion to U^{4+} by these released electrons. Thus initially one can expect a build-up of polyphasic areas of different U : Th ratios which on long annealing or prolonged exposure to UO_2 vapour would tend to homogenise. Such a process can explain the observed⁸ fact that the deposit on a ThO_2 pellet exposed to UO_2 vapour at 1400° for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. was diphasic; one cubic solid solution with a cell edge of $a_0 = 5.591 \text{ \AA}$ very close to pure ThO_2 and the other with $a_0 = 5.553 \text{ \AA}$ obviously richer in uranium (and possibly oxygen); after exposure for 24 hr. the deposit was monophasic with $a_0 = 5.515 \text{ \AA}$.

This reaction of the gaseous uranium oxide with ThO_2 substrate cannot be similarly interpreted if the gaseous species is assumed to be UO_4 with the T_d symmetry. The fourth oxygen at the apex of the tetrahedron would not allow for the maintenance of the stacking of layers with the cations of every layer lying exactly above one another. This might be considered as a possible evidence in favour of the vapourising species being UO_3 and against UO_4 .

The stabilized ZrO_2 has also the fluorite structure. However since the distribution of the cations is not uniform and the cations are not of the same size, all the sites are not equivalent. Hence the reaction though leading to solid solution formation is much slower than with pure ThO_2 . Both the monoclinic and the tetragonal ZrO_2 structures can be considered as having a deformed fluorite type structure. However in the latter structure the deformation is quite small tends and to decrease with increasing temperature until about 2000° after which complete cubic symmetry prevails. Thus one observes that the reaction with tetragonal ZrO_2 is hardly noticeable in about 3 hr. just above the monoclinic to tetragonal transformation temperature (1200°), but becomes noticeable at 1400° and above. While this might be partly due to the fact that the concentration of UO_2 also increases with temperature, it must be remembered that the concentration of gaseous UO_3 is sufficient to react strongly with ThO_2 and with the Ca-stabilized zirconia even at 1250° . It is therefore to be concluded that since the deviation from the fluorite structure is large in the case of both monoclinic ZrO_2 and HfO_2 , it is not possible to have matching sites and the reaction is not observed. As the deviation decreases and the tetragonal form becomes nearly cubic with the c/a ratio of 1.02, reaction proceeds sluggishly.

In the case of oxides with rocksalt structure CaO and CdO—the space group is also $F_{m\bar{3}m}$ and the point group symmetry of the cations with respect to the anions is also C_3 , hence a similar mechanism can be postulated. There is however one major difference as compared to the cubic RO_2 structures. In rocksalt structures, the anions are farther away from the cations (considering the {111} planes only) than for the fluorite structures, i.e., the rocksalt structure is a much more open structure. This is due to difference in the size and charge of the cations in the two cases, and consequently in the coordination numbers. It would thus be possible for the UO_3 molecule to even penetrate into the open rocksalt type structure. If the UO_3 molecules are considered to penetrate along the {111} direction in CaO, one would arrive at the $CaUO_4$ structure. This can be easily seen from the structures of solid UO_3 and $CaUO_4$ which are very similar⁹. In the UO_3 structure there are infinite chains of O-U-O-U-O linkages. These become finite in $CaUO_4$ with the Ca ions occupying intermediate sites (Fig. 2).

8. Karkhanavala, Momin, *J. Nucl. Materials*, 1964, 11, 114.

9. Wells, "Structural Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed., 1962, pp. 966ff. Oxford Univ. Press.

For an apparent chemical reaction to take place, two things are involved. First the initial reaction on the surface of the substrate, followed by the diffusion of either the incoming reactant or the surface product into the substrate or of the substrate atoms out of the surface product layer. In the above discussion the diffusion of cations over long distances within the host lattice leading to either solid solution or compound formation throughout the bulk of the solid is not considered. This diffusion into the bulk would be influenced by several factors, prominent among which would be the openness of the structure and the defect nature of the surface of the reactant or the products formed. The openness of the structure does seem to effect the reaction rate. In the most open BO_2 structures, compound formation takes place readily. The relative ease of the reaction with stabilized zirconia as compared to ZrO_2 could be facilitated by its comparatively more open structure. Thus the overall reaction with monoclinic zirconia could be imperceptibly slow, because even if the surface reaction did take place, diffusion into the dense packed monoclinic structure would be negligible. It is pertinent that Roberts¹⁰ has observed a very high mobility on the surface of orthorhombic $\text{ThO}_2\text{-U}_3\text{O}_8$ solid solutions. This could be due to high defect concentrations on such surfaces, and defects are known to accelerate reactions in the solid state.

APPLICATIONS

The large number of trivalent and tetravalent metal oxides with which urania (UO_2) forms a solid solution, possess at least one cubic modification of the fluorite or slightly deformed fluorite type. Thus rare-earth oxides like La_2O_3 , Ce_2O_3 , Pr_2O_3 , Nd_2O_3 , and Sm_2O_3 , which are known to form solid solutions with urania, crystallize with C-type R_2O_3 structure. It can be expected that in all these cases, the reaction would be faster and probably more complete if it is carried out with U_3O_8 in air at moderately high temperatures, i.e., with gaseous UO_2 , than with UO_2 in inert atmosphere even at much higher temperatures.

It is significant therefore to note the observation of Kolar, Handwerk and Beals¹¹, that with Nd_2O_3 and UO_2 solid solution formed readily in air but sluggishly and incompletely in hydrogen even up to 1650°C . This can now be understood and explained. In air during the heating to high temperatures, UO_2 would be oxidized to U_3O_8 (as was actually found by them as a second phase in some compositions) which in turn would form gaseous UO_2 for ready reaction with Nd_2O_3 . In hydrogen the reaction would be a true solid-state reaction between UO_2 and Nd_2O_3 and hence would be sluggish.

A similar observation has been made by Felton and Aitken¹² in the system $\text{UO}_2\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$.

The recently discovered sol-gel process¹³ of forming urania-thoria solid solutions has been applied even to other systems. By this process the solid solutions are formed at relatively low temperatures $900\text{-}1100^\circ$ in about four hours. For the ease with which the solid state reactions takes place at relatively low temperatures, this process takes advantage

10. Roberts, Aere, Harwell (Personal Communication).

11. Kolar, Handwerk and Beals, ANL-6631, Investigations in the system Urania-Neodymia, Argonne National Laboratory (U.S.A.), 1962.

12. Felton and Aitken, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 24, 35.

13. Ferguson, Arnold Ernst Jr., and Ean, Report ORNL-3225, Oak Ridge U.S.A. (1962).

primarily of the extreme reduction in particle size and consequent increase in surface area but as suggested by KarkhanaVala and Momin⁶ would get a further boost from the gaseous UO_2 that would be formed during the final heating in air.

It may thus be possible by taking into consideration (i) the possible gaseous intermediate products, and (ii) the symmetry of the substrate, to obtain reactions of UO_2 with other oxides with which pure solid state reactions are not possible or are sluggish.